

Секція III
«ПРОБЛЕМИ ЛІНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГІЇ ТА
МІЖКУЛЬТУРНОЇ КОМУНІКАЦІЇ»

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INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND CULTURE WHILE
LEARNING LANGUAGES

The term «language», according to Encyclopedia Britannica has been applied as a “system of conventional spoken, manual (signed), or written symbols by means of which human beings, as members of a social group and participants in its culture, express themselves. The functions of language include communication, the expression of identity, play, imaginative expression, and emotional release” [1]. Starting from a simple definition, one can understand that language can not exist out of culture. That is why this topic is widely considered as one of the most important issue of nowadays.

One of the researches said that «language is culture and culture is language», quite a deliberative statement. As everyone can see that the formation of language and culture is a simultaneous process that imposes influence on people’s lives. So, in order to understand one you need to be aware of the other.

We may also say, that the dynamical development of modern society with its cultural foundations is reflected in education, while the educational system reflects cultural condition of the entire society. Now learning languages is one of the most popular directions as it is worth remembering that learning a language starts from the culture of the country where the language originated from. The learner must understand that language reflects cultural traditions, customs and lifestyle so in order to understand the language you need to start off with learning culture.

A personal growth arises in a cultural field that is a space of its activity. In this respect, language is perceived as an essential part of culture. These two concepts can not be separated as everything that a person created is denoted by language and all cultural products display due to a person's ability to use language in all its functions.

Speaking of functions, it is worth mentioning that among its main – communicative function, linguists also define cumulative function, which more precisely shows the relation between language and culture. The language in this

function is an interlink between generations which acts as a “deposit” of knowledge and the mean of transmitting extra linguistic collective experience. The most clearly cumulative function is displayed in the field of vocabulary, as it is directly related to objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality [2]. Vocabulary reflects the fragments of social experience determined by someone’s main activity.

Let’s take a look at some colors in different languages, as they convey symbolic meanings to everyday life. For instance, we associate gray color in Russian language with daily routine. A good example can be shown through what we refer to as "gray days" (Rus. серые будни) when nothing seems remarkable about given days. In England, however, the gray color symbolizes nobility, elegance, thus, it sheds completely different connotations.

Another example of colors, is white. In Russian language, white is the symbol of purity and happiness, while in the East it is considered as the color of mourning.

Moreover, one must realize that learning a specific language through culture would not only help us acquire language skills, but also reconsider ways on how to perceive it.

References:

1. David Crystal and Robert Henry Robins. Language. – Encyclopedia Britannica, inc., 2020.
2. Леонтьев А. А. Национально-культурная специфика речевого поведения. - М., Наука, 1977.

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The present paper aims to present how tight the connection between language and culture especially in term of learning new specific language. As one must understand that our activities are denoted by language and the way to display them is possible through language itself. We also put into consideration accumulative function of the language as one of the aspects that explain how language and culture are connected while learning new languages.

Key words: *language, culture, learning languages, accumulative function*